

The Great Economic Balance and its Social Impact

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The behavior of a country's economic policies and its solid financial position have always been considered key factors in its economy. It is also necessary to examine the organizational structure, international trade, the population factor in technological development and innovation, and short- and long-term investment projects. All these factors can be grouped into a useful tool in state management, controlling and projecting its income versus expenses, ensuring economic stability, and reducing social inequality. Fiscal policy is the way a government manages its income and covers part of its obligations, shaping the economy and giving back to the population through investments funded by taxes. The state has the obligation to reinvest these taxes in the same taxpayers, covering needs such as health, education, social investment, and potable water, commonly known as public spending.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fiscal policy is an extremely important tool that allows governments to manage resources based on tax collection. It is considered that the proper management of a fiscal policy is a resource that facilitates measuring the state's debt capacity and liquidity.

This governmental policy automatically adjusts to the economic needs generated by basic market activities (trade, industry, services, mining, and agriculture). A defined fiscal policy stabilizes the position and image of a country before the world, supports population income, guarantees consumer compliance with obligations, maintains order, and helps reduce the pressure caused by inflation.

According to [1], basically, the Government uses this tool to collect money, mainly through taxes, and then decides how to spend it, such as on healthcare, education, or infrastructure. This expenditure is known as public spending.

The objective of these measures is for the economy to grow stably, cover certain basic needs, and influence the economy to achieve goals such as reducing unemployment or controlling inflation. It achieves this using two instruments: public spending and taxes.

Fiscal policy stabilizes a country's economy by generating growth and foreign investment, supporting the education sector, and developing and improving the physical and structural systems necessary for economic activities and the population's quality of life, including communication routes such as roads, bridges, modern transportation systems, expanded energy networks, water supply, primary and specialized healthcare services, schools, and universities.

The management of this tool is vital for a country's wealth to be balanced and for business bankruptcy to be mitigated, combining fiscal policy with monetary policy, which forms the dynamics of equilibrium economics.

For [2], politics, economics, and the international system share the idea that economic globalization is not a manifestation of market evolution but was designed and created with a specific objective that is, to deify economic values above all other values, aggressively inserting and codifying these values worldwide.

The pace of market integration was very fast and disorganized, making it impossible to adapt and perhaps respond better to new challenges, especially for less developed countries.

2. METHOD

The methodology used in this research is descriptive, providing a qualitative approach and employing a documentary strategy supported by investigative consultations on the web. This facilitated the management of information related to the main subject of the document, reviewing theories concerning the research topic, its regulatory profile, and professional competence.

The material used to collect information included the doctoral study plans currently being undertaken and which are available on the institution's web pages. The documentary technique used in the research aims to gather data from theories that support the economy of a state and its regulatory policies, allowing differentiation of concepts from various authors and their publications.

This research also includes an analysis of secondary sources from some countries in Europe, America, and Asia, focusing on their economic behavior, per capita income, and financial indicators, to measure economic stability and fiscal policy management. This results in a relevant insight for the reader regarding the quality of life in each country included in the investigation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Difference Between Automatic and Discretionary Fiscal Policy

If we ask ourselves why taxes are paid, the simple answer is that, unless a better idea emerges, taxation is the only practical means of raising revenue to finance public spending on goods and services demanded by most people [3]. However, establishing a fair and efficient tax system is not simple, particularly in developing countries seeking integration into the global economy. In these countries, the ideal tax system would collect essential revenue without excessive public debt and do so without discouraging economic activity or deviating too much from the tax systems of other countries.

When changes arise in economic activities that directly affect a country's productivity, it is necessary to have support that guarantees consumption according to demand needs and maintains economic stability. As the number of consumers increases, income generation also increases, and with it, the generation of rents and higher tax collection. This is known as automatic fiscal policy, specifically the automatic increase in consumption. It is clear that when taxpayers have money to spend, consumption increases, which slows inflationary pressure. This is a strategy applied by governments when changes directly affect a country's economy to avoid economic recession, unemployment, and increased insecurity.

The stabilizing effects of fiscal policy are a characteristic of economic equilibrium, reflected in adjustments of various fiscal variables in relation to fluctuations in real output, that is, in a relationship between endogenous variables [4]. If it is assumed that there is an exogenous source of instability, the dynamic equilibrium of the economy may follow an unstable or explosive path, and at the same time, fiscal policy may have stabilizing effects in each period.

Automatic stabilizers work by providing balance, adjusting contradictorily and influentially when an economic recession occurs. When there is market weakness, it is necessary to stimulate consumer demand. Automatic stabilizers are characterized by being rapidly adaptable to the market. It is common for an automatic stabilizer to immediately mitigate accumulated risks due to increased inflationary pressure. The most notable effects are increased unemployment due to reduced income from demand; in this case, the state must increase and promote benefits that directly mitigate the lack of employment through subsidies to companies and contributions that cover the social security of the labor sector.

Another aspect that arises from inflationary pressure is tax progressivity. The state is forced to seek resources to meet financing needs and promote economic stability. However, increasing taxes at a certain point does not counteract inflation and may cause consumers to reduce their purchasing power, slowing the economy as a negative effect. Cutting public spending would be more advisable.

Social Security policies protect workers from potential income falls caused by health problems, unemployment, or old age [5]. Illness limits work capacity and affects people financially due to treatment costs or job loss. Prolonged unemployment can cause poverty, as can old age, when work capacity is reduced. Therefore, Social Security has the mission of protecting workers from these events, seeking to prevent income loss.

The state must create strategies that improve government programs covering transfer payments in social security and health services for the most vulnerable groups. A solidarity economy—benefiting cooperatives, foundations, mutual associations, and nonprofit corporations—can create support for households suffering economic weakness due to unemployment, lack of income, or old age. When health limitations increase, the economic effect is immediate due to high treatment costs and a lack of healthcare resources.

As previously stated, Public Administrations carry out essential functions in the economy: redistributing national income and wealth through taxes and transfers, and producing non-marketable services for the public by making investment and consumption expenditures [6]. In their redistributive function, fiscal policy

has stabilizing effects if, through the tax and transfer system, it ensures that private sector disposable income fluctuates less than national income throughout the economic cycle. That is, if it reduces fluctuations in disposable income for the private sector, helping to sustain it during recession phases and limiting its growth during expansion phases.

The most relevant advantages of stabilizing economic effects include the absence of the need for discretionary governmental actions, reduced delays in economic activities, and preventing the economy from entering recession due to a lack of guarantees and support in the market. Among the disadvantages, a substantial increase in state budgets must be recognized to provide economic support, which sacrifices resources designated for population welfare. If unemployment benefits are too high or generous, people may choose not to work, affecting productivity and resulting in activities of primary need. Changes in public spending with increased taxes during economic expansion give rise to discretionary fiscal policy.

The effectiveness of discretionary fiscal policy measures depends on a broad set of factors, some of which may vary significantly throughout the economic cycle [7]. This may cause fiscal multipliers to change over time.

The depth and characteristics of the current crisis, with generalized restrictions on credit availability, encouraged the adoption of major fiscal stimulus packages in many countries, which appear to have had positive short-term effects on activity and employment.

Among the measures taken as a result of discretionary fiscal policy is influencing demand through public spending to increase market activity and curb economic instability. This also increases public works schemes. It is often described that a country with continuous public works generates jobs, and with job creation comes income, thereby creating aggregate demand.

To calculate aggregate demand, the same methods used to calculate GDP can be applied; however, aggregate demand is associated with spending. Therefore, it is calculated using the product method, that is, from the perspective of what society has spent [8]. This calculation includes household spending (individuals), investment spending, public administration spending, and finally, net exports, which are the difference between imports and exports.

An economy in uncontrolled growth generates inflation, causing a bubble in the prices of goods, which requires immediate governmental action. Governments must adjust public spending and tax collection to avoid damaging the stability and efficiency of the economy. Stimuli are necessary in this process to strengthen the economy and make the economic slowdown less severe. Governments may implement tax cuts to increase consumption. A state must recognize the economic problem, verify its cause and effect, and implement an economic policy that stimulates production in the face of unemployment and creates confidence in demand.

3.2 Taxes and Conditional Spending Cushion the Economic Cycle

Reducing public spending and increasing taxes results in shifting aggregate demand, decreasing consumption capacity, and conditioning spending to cushion the economic cycle. When income exceeds spending, the government budget tends to show a surplus. When spending exceeds income, the government tends to show a deficit. A clear example of a deficit is spending \$1.2 billion USD compared with income of \$1 billion USD. The result is a contractionary fiscal policy that slows economic growth, reduces job creation, decreases income, increases taxes, and leaves companies without resources to invest, which reduces demand and decelerates the economy.

Finally, one of the most notable characteristics of contractionary fiscal policy is related to how it is determined, and it is precisely the fiscal impulse indicator that makes this determination possible [9]. In this sense, Nelson Salazar argues that fiscal impulse is an economic indicator that quantifies what is known as

fiscal discretion. Therefore, it distinguishes between economic changes derived from natural economic cycles —also known as automatic stabilizers— and those that result from the imposition of discretionary fiscal policy.

The structure of expenses and income generated by the state by imposing tax obligations to stabilize the economy due to changes that arise across periods affecting economic indicators must first be monitored concerning the long- and short-term structure of aggregate demand. Secondly, comparisons must be made between different countries and period changes resulting from fiscal policy effects. Ultimately, the discretionary stance adopted by fiscal policy, whether expansionary or restrictive, must be verified. Aggregate demand generates greater investment, increased consumption, increased public spending, and increased taxes; people tend to have more money to spend and consume. Creating an increase in aggregate demand may be a positive option for economic growth in a country, but it carries the risk of generating inflation.

3.3 Discretionary Measures to Reduce the Budget Deficit

Finally, Argentina, Korea, and Russia, from the onset of their respective crises, broke away from the economic policy restrictions imposed by the adoption of the neoliberal strategy [10]. Thus, the economic policy response of each economy consisted of a set of measures prioritizing the reactivation of the real economy over restoring market sentiment confidence. In this context, the implementation of expansionary fiscal policy stood out, contributing to the restoration of effective demand and sustained post-crisis economic growth. The empirical evidence presented here supports the proposal that expansionary fiscal policy is important for economic growth, particularly during and after an economic crisis, especially when accompanied by appropriate complementary policies such as expansionary monetary and credit policies.

In an expansionary fiscal policy, more jobs are created, and more investment and infrastructure contracts are executed. It is common for the population to have more money to spend, generating an increase in demand, injecting more resources into the market, and consequently higher tax collection, accelerating economic growth, and stimulating private investment. This creates greater opportunities for job creation, investor incentives through tax benefits, technological development, and improved quality of life for the population.

State budgets must be controlled. Governments generally spend or invest more than they receive in tax revenue. In political contexts, especially elections, candidates include promises about public spending and speculate about tax reductions to gain voter support and popularity in the election outcomes. However, they often lack a clear balance of state finances, resulting in irreparable mistakes.

3.4 Discretionary Fiscal Policy to Stimulate the Economy

If we consider that economic policy also encompasses monetary policy as a tool that affects the interest rate through discretionary management of the money supply by the monetary authority, then this can affect the income level by influencing investment preferences based on interest rate movements [11].

Discretionary fiscal policy is characterized by a lag between implementation and the moment its effects occur, creating an expansionary bias, where spending continues to increase and taxes decrease. This policy is difficult to implement. No state wants to cut its funds designated for sustaining and supporting its people. Education, security, health, potable water, and roads are priorities for a state, and maintaining stability in these areas is necessary.

Governments must implement tax benefits and stimulate investment without fiscal burden, deducting obligations and increasing investment budgets in public spending. These measures create employment, foster consumption, and promote investment.

3.5 Fiscal Stimuli Can Crowd Out Investment

Tax incentives and direct financial assistance (subsidies and/or subsidized loans) for research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) activities are two commonly used public intervention instruments aimed at stimulating companies' innovation efforts [12].

Crowding-out effects in an expansionary policy occur when a government borrows from abroad, and debt is reflected not only in the amount acquired but also in interest rates, which reduce private sector investment. Discretionary fiscal policy is based on applying the budget and tax regulations for revenue collection. Fiscal stimuli may crowd out investment when increased public spending leads to increased demand for credit, raises interest rates, and affects private company investment due to high financial costs.

In a state, fiscal stimuli through temporary tax reductions are necessary to boost consumption and alleviate citizens' financial burdens. Infrastructure investment programs generate employment. Modernizing roads and building bridges improves territorial communication, modernizes transportation systems, and directs cash transfers to citizens to support consumption and mitigate the economic effects of crises.

Fiscal stimuli are considered a contribution that attracts investors through subsidies and tax exemptions, reducing taxes. They are tools used by countries to promote economic activity and increase participation in the international market. They generally have highly positive effects but can also generate distortions that affect resource allocation in investment across economic sectors, society, and culture.

Based on the interpretation that fiscal stimuli are economic benefits granted by tax law to the taxpayer for specific economic policy and social interest purposes, this work aims to analyze and reflect on the effect of applying facilities, exceptions by economic sector, and fiscal stimuli established in the federation's revenue law for determining income tax for individuals and legal entities in the agricultural sector across various income levels [13].

3.6 Mechanisms of Displacement

When private capital is diverted, the state favors certain sectors through tax benefits; investors thereby channel resources toward areas that, according to indicator data, position themselves as the most profitable and sustainable assets in the stock market in both the short and long term. Companies receiving tax incentives can operate with advantages over others that do not, which may negatively affect and decelerate investment in non-subsidized sectors.

As a result of the study conducted, knowing all the tax incentives to which taxpayers under the Tax Regime for agricultural activities are entitled is of utmost importance, since by applying them, Income Tax (ISR) could be considerably reduced; additionally, Value Added Tax (VAT) could even be requested for reimbursement, thereby generating additional income to the company's cash flow, ultimately strengthening its finances. This, in turn, may lead to greater growth capacity, acquisition of infrastructure, personnel hiring, and reduction of liabilities, among other benefits [14]. Through these support schemes, the federal government seeks to boost the most important sectors in our country, and one of the best ways of doing so is by reducing the tax burden on such taxpayers.

The incentives that persist in companies dependent on state support reduce their capacity to innovate or compete in open markets. This impact tends to concentrate on attracting investment to areas affected by conflict, poverty, and limited implementation of technological means, thereby hindering economic strengthening and generating imbalances in fiscal policy. This is considered a negative displacement of investments. Fundamentally, every tax incentive must be aligned with the objectives of sustainable development, fostering competition and innovation in regions and sectors with potential for economic and productive development.

Figure 1. World Bank country classification by income level corresponding to 2024–2025 [15]

Figure 2. World Bank country classification by income level [15]

The World Bank's income data (2024–2025) and its country classification by income level constitute a fundamental tool for comparative analysis of global economic development [15].

This classification, updated annually on the first (01) of July each year, is based on Gross National Income (GNI) per capita, calculated using the Atlas method, which adjusts monetary values for inflation and the average exchange rate over the last three periods.

For the 2024–2025 period, the World Bank divides economies into four categories:

- Low income: less than USD 1,135
- Lower-middle income: between USD 1,136 and USD 4,465
- Upper-middle income: between USD 4,466 and USD 13,845
- High income: more than USD 13,845

This system not only makes it possible to identify the level of economic development of each country, but also reveals regional trends and territorial conditions. For example, in Latin America and the Caribbean, the proportional income increase among countries has been very high, rising from 9% —common in indicator data since 1987— to 44% in 2023, demonstrating a significant improvement across territories and providing a standardized view of relative economic progress among countries.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It is necessary to reach an agreement regarding the precise definition of engineering in order to organize program offerings and structure adequate mathematical content for them.

There is a generalized consensus that engineering students need to develop mathematical competencies; the concern lies in determining what type of mathematics they require and when. The education system needs a profound restructuring, to the extent that most participants agree that it is better to establish a new

training system—one that truly functions as a system—that involves and demands accountability from each of its subsystems.

Mathematics education, regulations, entry and exit frameworks, updates in teaching and professional practice, its articulation with other learning processes in engineering, and an evaluation framework to determine the achievement of learning outcomes must be clearly defined.

Theoretical and practical content are priorities because academia and industry are far from reaching a point of agreement: for the former, engineers must master mathematical conceptualization; for the latter, what is needed is the development of logical-interpretative and abstract capabilities to analyze, understand, and utilize the results of computational calculations.

It is necessary to evaluate methodologies and teaching approaches for mathematics, because today's students have different expectations from before, and they must be motivated to study engineering. This implies a change in teachers' mindsets, extensive curriculum restructuring, and the internationalization of content, in addition to improving the social perception of engineering, regulating professional practice, and raising compensation levels.

After the technological revolution of the 20th century, the New World Order impacted all areas of social development, including education. Today, technology must be considered an ally for teaching and enhancing mathematics in both schools and industry; that is, we must move from pencil-and-paper calculations to computational methods, since these are everyday tools for engineers.

Engineering must once again become a profession of high value and social and corporate recognition, which has been lost due to the excessive supply of programs—many of which are not truly engineering programs—and due to the lack of leadership and state policies. Furthermore, professional associations do not assume their responsibility and instead align with government bodies and universities to maintain and sponsor their initiatives.

If teachers continue working with exercises rather than with problems to train students in mathematics, they will prevent students from enhancing and innovating their knowledge in IT. A more attractive alternative is to use Challenge-Based and Project-Based Learning, as these approaches create opportunities for students to integrate mathematics with other learning processes they receive.

The generalized perception demonstrated by students in this research regarding mathematics in engineering curricula is that mathematics courses are an imposition, not a necessity. This is partly due to the number of programs marketed as engineering when they are not, and to the structuring of the mathematics core around curricula belonging to programs that are indeed engineering.

Engineering is an area of knowledge with multiple interrelations with other fields; therefore, its professionals should be trained by incorporating principles of Complex Thinking, such as Transdisciplinarity and multidimensionality.

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